

Efficacy of Video Assisted Teaching on the Knowledge Relating to Child Abuse among School - Going Children

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Abstract:-

Background: A child is abused when they are exposed to sexually, psychologically, or physically threatening situations. **Method:** A Quantitative Research design was used in this study. Purposive sampling technique was used for the selection of 120 students from Sarvodaya Bal Vidhyalay, Delhi. Data was obtained using self-administered Knowledge questionnaire. **Result:** there was statistically significant mean difference for knowledge score observed between experimental group and control group during post-test. **Conclusion:** Since child abuse leads to lifelong impairment of child's physical and mental health which ultimately affects the country's economic and social development, so there is a need to increase awareness of children regarding child abuse which can help in preventing them.

Keywords: Knowledge, Child Abuse, School Going Children, Video Assisted Teaching.

I. INTRODUCTION

A major increase in awareness of child abuse in the twentieth century was seen, especially physical abuse, sexual abuse, emotional abuse, and neglect. The belief that children are the parents' property has led to beaten and abandoned children for thousands of years in economically wealthy countries.¹

A "Ministry of Women and Child Development" (GOI) study on "Child Abuse: India 2007" states that children who are between the ages of five and twelve are particularly at risk for abuse and exploitation in all forms of abuse.²

Today, abuse of every kind is common. Aside from domestic violence, rape, sexual harassment, incest, and institutional abuse, hate crimes can also occur in a variety of places.³

Any behaviour, oversight, or carelessness by a person, whether an adult or a kid, that seriously jeopardises a child's survival and development and has a lasting harmful impact on the child's physical and psychological well-being is referred to as child abuse.⁴

It is very important for children to have knowledge regarding all types of abuse and so the researcher thought to improve the knowledge of children through video-assisted teaching.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To identify the effectiveness of video-assisted teaching on knowledge relating to child abuse among school-going children in selected school of Delhi.

➤ Hypothesis:

H 1: There is a significant mean difference found between pre-test and post-test knowledge at 0.05 level of significance.

III. MATERIAL AND METHODS

To accomplish the objectives of the research, a quasi-experimental research design was adopted to evaluate the effectiveness of video assisted teaching on the knowledge relating to child abuse among school- going children at Sarvodaya Bal Vidhyalay, New Seelampur, Delhi. A total of 120 samples were recruited by adopting the purposive sampling technique. The data was collected in the month of June 2022.

➤ Ethical Consideration:

- Administrative permission was taken from concerned Schools Dean to conduct the study followed by ethical clearance from Sharda University.
- Informed consent was taken from the participant. Participants were ensured that Anonymity and Confidentiality will be maintain.

➤ *Tools:*

For the data collection, demographic Performa, questionnaire to assess the knowledge regarding child abuse.

IV. STATICAL ANALYSIS

The data was organized in a master sheet and tabulated. The data analysis was done by using Statistical package EZR, version 2.4-0.

V. RESULT

Findings of the study were organized and presented under the following sections:

- *Section 1: Socio-demographic variables*
- *Section 2: Knowledge of school going children on child abuse*

➤ *Section-1 Socio-demographic variables*

Majority of the school going children were more than 13 years of age i.e. 31.7% in study group and 34.2% in control group. Most of them were Male i.e. 36.7% in study group and 32.5% in control group. Most of them were from Muslim religion i.e. 21.7% in study

+ group and 19.2% in control group. Majority of the participants had two siblings i.e. 18.3% in study group and 17.5% in control group. Majority of the participants were first born i.e. 33.3% in study group and 30% in control group. Majority of the children were living with both the parents i.e. 45% in study group and 46.7% in control group. Majority of the participant’s father had their education till 12th std. i.e. 24.2% in study group and 25 % in control group. Majority of the participant’s mother had their education till 10th std. i.e. 35.8% in study group and 31.7% in control group. Majority of the participant’s father had private job i.e. 19.2% in study group and 15% in control group. Majority of the participant’s mother were Housewife i.e. 26.7% in study group and 25.8% in control group. Majority of the participant’s family income were 10,000-20,000 i.e. 26.7% in study group and 31.7% in control group. Majority of the participants were living in nuclear family i.e. 26.7% in study group and 25.8% in experimental group. Most of the participants had less than 4 members in their family i.e. 19.2% in study group and 17.5% in control group. Majority of the participant’s sources of information were from parents i.e. 18.3% in study group and 13.3% in control group. Both groups were similar (Homogenous) in their baseline characteristics ($p>0.05$)

Table 1 Mean, Standard deviation and Homogeneity comparison of the Baseline measures among school going children in study group and control group. (N=120)

Outcome measures	Group				Mean Difference	Independent t-Test & p value
	Study (60)		Control (60)			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Knowledge score	10.05	3.00	10.92	3.63	0.867	t=1.425, p=0.157(NS)

($P>0.05$ Not Significant) NS: Non- Significant

Data presented in Table 1 depicts that the mean knowledge score of both groups were similar at the baseline it was formed by performing independent t-test.

➤ *Section-2 Knowledge of school going children on child abuse*

Table 2 Comparison of Pre-test and Post-tests – Mean and Standard Deviation of knowledge scores among school going children in study group and control group

Knowledge Score at time-points	Study group			Control group			Mean Difference	Independent t-test & p value
	n	M	SD	n	M	SD		
Pre-test (n=120)	60	10.05	3.00	60	10.92	3.633	0.42	t= 1.425 p=0.157
Post-test (n=120)	60	17.48	4.806	60	15.02	3.186	2.46	t=3.313 p=0.01(S)

($P>0.05$ Not Significant) NS: Non- Significant, S: Significance

Table 2 depicts that there is statistically significant mean difference noted in knowledge score at post-test between study group and control group. Independent t-test was computed to find out the significant mean difference. This shows that video assisted teaching is an effective intervention in improving the knowledge on child abuse among school going children in study group. Hence the researcher failed to accept null hypothesis.

VI. DISCUSSION

The present study revealed that the mean post-test knowledge score (17.48) was significantly greater than mean pre-test knowledge score (10.05) of study group. The p value is 0.01 that is significant. The study was supported by sajjie, et.al revealed that finding of study revealed that the mean post-test knowledge score (20.06) was significantly greater than the mean pre-test knowledge score (10.24) of experimental group of students.⁵

This study is also supported by Singh, N, Wimmy, j (2020) revealed that the mean and SD of posttest knowledge score was (19.97 ± 1.79) and pretest knowledge score was (13.57 ± 3.32) . The paired 't' value (21.142) was found to be significant.⁶

There is a chance that children under the age of 18 may be abused. In the context of a relationship of responsibility, trust, or power, it includes all types of emotional and/or physical abuse, sexual abuse, recklessness, neglect, and commercial or other exploitation that actually or potentially harm the child's health, survival, development, or dignity.⁷

VII. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The limitation of the study was as follows;

- The study was conducted only in two school, one for pilot and another one for main study
- Only 6,7 and 8 classes were the participants.
- Sample size was small, hence, findings cannot be generalized.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Since child abuse leads to lifelong impairment of child's physical and mental health which ultimately affects the country's economic and social development, hence, the researcher found a need to improve the knowledge of children regarding child abuse as improvement in knowledge can help in prevention of child abuse. Also, the researcher found out that the video assisted teaching was effective in improving the knowledge on child abuse among school-going children.

Conflict of interest: Nil

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